

NOVELS THAT CREATE ADDITIONAL NARRATIVE STRUCTURES. (THE ICE PALACE)

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ABSTRACT

This article found that the image of S. Fitzgerald's The Ice palace novella is given in support of the abstract author's speech in the pictures. In Narrator's implicit depiction, all methods of storytelling are preserved. The narrator of the events revealed the selection of elements (characters, situations, messages, including personal speeches, thoughts, rational perceptions) as narrative material to injure the event. The article also features a commentary on Sally Carroll's story, her life in the South, and her dislike of the North.

In the cognitive analysis of S. Fitzgerald's short stories, "narrator criteria" are always important because the story is "structured" from his point of view and the events are also seen through his eyes.

The novel "The Ice Palace" is one of the first works of S. Fitzgerald and was published in 1920. In the novel, the abstract author with his southern modality and beliefs is clearly represented. The six chapters of the novella from the life of Sally Carroll, in the form of six episodes, are structured into six spaces, with the clearly defined boundaries of "south" and "north" as well as the characters hidden within them. Moreover, as for the Southern narrator-characters, S. Fitzgerald also "includes" a typical southern pronunciation in their lexicon, and A.I. Poltoraykits notes in his comment: "mawnin = morning: In this and other episodes of the story, the

pronunciation of the southern dialect of whites is graphically occurs. This dialect is presented in its spoken version, auxiliary verbs and articles are omitted, elliptical expressions, abbreviated forms are used ... Spose = Surpase = Lo = Hallo "[Poltoratskiy, 1979, 315].

The novella begins with the creation of the Southern space: colors, sounds, calm, even drowsy: "The sunlight dripped over the house like golden paint over an art jar and the freckling shadows here and there only intensified the rigor of the bath of light" [1, p.72] The author weaves a non-existent southern city called Tarlton in the southernmost corner of the (real) state of Georgia and clearly indicates the time: "September, afternoon". The protagonists of the works live in this sleepy city. The abstract author slowly introduces the protagonist to the girl, who then becomes

the narrator herself. This method is specific to this novella in the first two parts. This is how portraits are created, first the abstract author creates it, then the narrator prevails: "Up her bedroom window Sally Carroll Harper rested her nineteen year old chin on a fifty two year old sill and wathed Clark Darrows ancient Ford turn the corner" [1, p.72] This novella is highly structured, divided into narrative areas, and can be classified as an "implicit narrative": The implicit image of the narrator involves all the ways of constructing a story. 1. An event is the selection of elements (characters, situations, events, including the speech, thoughts, and perceptions of the characters) as narrative material to create an event that is narrated from events "[Schmidt, 2003, 67].

In fact, the center of the whole story is Sally Carroll's story, her life in the South, and her dislike of the North. If only the "abstract author" prevailed in the novella "The Ice Palace", then the personal beginning, the high level of emotionality of the statement would be lost. All assessments of the characters are given on the descriptive boundary between the abstract author and Sally Carroll's perception, even the portrait: "She approached a mirror, regarded her expression with a pleased and pleasant languor, dabbed two spots of rouge on her lips and a grain of powder on her nose and covered her bobbed corn colored hair with a rose littered sunbonnet "[1, p.73]. We emphasize that the writer creates a portrait - Sally Carroll's actions, her self-loathing, her satisfaction with her appearance, that is, she creates a narrative portrait. At the same time, the rhythmic beginning, the repetition of the "oath" and the whole "speed" of the

process, formed by epithets from the "abstract author" are involved. As E. Farino points out, the external portrait of a character is "just a detail of a great whole. The appearance of a person is one of the intensive semiotic phenomena of any culture "[Farino, 2004, 182].

Then the researcher points to the possibilities of a moving portrait in a statement that transforms a "momentary state image into a changing frame of a particular state of mind". This assertion is also true of S. Fitzgerald's heroes, including Sally Carroll. S. Fitzgerald allows such a narrator, a girl from the South, who is a romantic recipient of the history of the Civil War, to make a contrasting assessment of the North and South, the North and the South. Therefore, the emotional portrait - perceptions change, evolve depending on his state of mind. In the first chapter, entitled "The South," Fitzgerald allows Sally Carroll to describe her objections to the South, describing her desire to leave: "... because I couldn't ever marry you. , but tied down here I'd get restless.I'd feel I was - wastin myself .There are two sides to me, you see.There is the sleepy old side you love..."[1, p.77]

The abstract author says that this monologue takes place in a slow-moving car through the cotton fields in the warmth of sleep: "like a great warm nourishing bosom for the infant earth". A walk in the cemetery with a loved one is also depicted as a pastel-painted, extraordinary love, a landscape devoid of emotional negativity: "gray, white and golden - green under the cheerful late sun."

Sally Carroll's sense of love defines the whole episode's attitude, and it is her

proactive narrative that characterizes the whole scene, as Harry's northern affection can be so intense: "I see through your precious eyes. You're beautiful now, so I know she must have been" [1, p.78]. It is the northern romantic Marjorie Lee, who is in love with the South, who can express his love in the buried cemetery. S. Fitzgerald prepares an antithesis of everything (space, time, air level, dialogue tone, and even the characters) in a series of episodes: South and North. It's no coincidence that Sally Carroll describes herself as follows: "I'm a summer child. I don't like any cold. I've ever seem". The word "any cold" will be the most used detail by narrator Sally Carroll in the following "northern" chapters of the novel, both literally and figuratively. It should be noted that he understands the North as an alien space with alien morals. Therefore, in these chapters, the "abstract author" directs the flow of the story, which is complemented by the narrator's rejection of the "stranger," and emotional negativity also occurs when the nature and colors behind the train window change and become unbearably cold: "All night in the Pullman it was very cold... white hills and valleys and scattered pines whose every branch was a green platter for a cold feast of snow" [1, p.80]. Even her lover doesn't feel like Sally Carroll did before: "icy - cold face kissed her."

NV Maksimova's article "Communicative dominants of speech style" gives descriptions of the modeling of the linguistic personality, ie the narrator's speech image in the context of modeling the feelings of "own and other": this opposition defines the typological material with zero, boundary "[Maksimova, 2005, 96]. This is just an "abstract author" area of

commentary, and its representation is also almost zero. The narrator's territory is always saturated with a module of emotional negativity: ... "I am another" model of thinking. These feelings are the central part that defines the area of speech formation that is maximally occurring - the part that is bounded (contrasted) by the text-mentative area of response. 1. As a chronotopic story, it is connected with the logical-semantic basis of the narrative, which is opposed to the narrative "[Maksimova, 2005, 96]. Sally Carroll's disapproval of even an orderly and elegant library space is described as an unconscious comparison to her beloved, less-than-rich, but heart-warming space created with kindness and warmth. There are many positive qualities in the constructed "perception, perception": "Sally Carroll had an instantaneous vision of the battered old library at home... and the old couch that had been mended up for forty five years and was still luxurious to dream in" [1, p.81]. The rejection process is also related to the character system, as Harry begins to teach his mistress how to behave, what to say in public. Sally Carroll's meaningful denial of "she whispered insinuating herself into her arms" and the "cracks" in her true feelings and relationships: "And as she said this she had the feeling for almost the first time in her life that she was acting a part" Taking into account the imbalance between [1, p.83], the abstract author emphasizes that the protagonist "knows" the situation and thoughts of the girl.

Regarding the narratological point of view, V. Schmidt writes: "We define this concept as a node of conditions that create external and internal factors that affect the reception and transmission of events. The

term "future" refers to the relationship between events and an understanding perspective "[Schmidt, 2004, 121].

The events described, that is, Sally Carroll's disapproval of the whole complex, from individuals to climate, from the history of the North to its mentality, are the object of view. Therefore, we agree with W. Schmidt: "There is no history without a point of view. History (event) cannot exist on its own unless narrative material is the object of "look" or "perspective" "[Schmidt, 2003, 121].

It can be said that the whole modeling system that characterizes the freedom and naturalness of Sally Carroll's behavior is in a romantic mood. It blends in with the whole look of the South. But in the North, as Harry's henchman, he's a strange, alien element, so the abstract author uses the word "stranger" a lot. That is why S. Fitzgerald sees each episode as "his" or "domestic" antithesis. Even the professor likes Sally Carroll because she's a southerner. S. Fitzgerald does not create detailed portraits of relatives. They are shaped as the narrator's "portrait-impression": his favorite "she met a big gray-haired man" and Harry's mother "lady who was like an egg" metaphorically perceived by the girl. Needless to say, this disapproval then escalated to the point of complete disgust. As for the professor, the author predetermines the whole tone of the free conversation (as in the informal South): "She liked him immediately a reddish brown mustache under watery blue eyes...". As we can see, this is the first portrait in paint, because all the other characters are colorless - they are the ones wrapped in fur. The professor's point of view is also unique, you can "gossip" with him on any topic,

gossip about the snowdrift and his style of classifying people. This novella is rich in dialogues where the narrator prioritizes, emphasizing originality and naturalness. However, the abstract author "leaves the story, the event, when there is an exchange of ideas between people who are spiritually close to each other. Otherwise - it will be necessary to interpret the psychological and emotional state of the narrator. The professor's comments on "northern nervousness" are no different from the point of view of the protagonist, which helps to sound the same word that has already formed an opinion: "Why do you live here if it is so depressing?". Translator V. Kharitonov finds a more expressive description: "Why are you now living in this disgrace?" The abstract author always creates a cold and colorless environment to illustrate Sally Carroll's attitude: "she trembled involuntarily as her cold lips kissed the tip of her ear".

S. Fitzgerald builds his story in the North in such a way that every trivial detail becomes an event, and every small episode becomes the next step for the main event. That's why the "repeat" method is so important. In this regard, it is appropriate to agree with the opinion of V. Tyupa, who wrote in the work "Essays on Modern Narratology": Here, even homogeneity, repetition, and obvious inaccuracy are important events, but not in terms of the referential phenomenon of what is being told, but within the communicative phenomenon of narration "[Tyupa, 2002, 13,]. That's why "repetitions" show Sally Carroll maintaining a temporary distance in receiving characters.

According to long-term and close acquaintances, this is the case, and

comparisons such as “Lady who was Like an egg” can be defined as another important condition for the narrator’s self-description, his figurative imagination. The mutual dislike between the future bride and mother-in-law is obvious. So the abstract author simply notes: “She knew also that Harry’s mother disapproved of her bobbed hair.” As mentioned above, the linguistic stylistic self-description reduces the participation of the abstract author, while the characters in the dialogues are embodied more vividly. Harry and Sally’s dialogue about the virtues of the northerners takes place in the veil of uncompromising rivals, not in the tone of lovers’ kindness. Sally Carroll’s tone and demeanor of speech are not characterized by sharpness or rudeness. But when she hears Harry talking nonsense about all the southerners, Sally’s endurance ends: “Hush your mouth, Harry! - she cried angrily”. The theme of the South is also repeated and varied (in the debate, the comparison of the faint solar disk with its luminous brother in Tarlton, etc.), and even the discourse transport revives old sentiments: “Away, away. Away down South in Dixie”. It’s also important to emphasize the modified costumes, as the abstract author always emphasizes that all characters are accustomed to fur coats as if depriving them of individuality, and even a handshake is impossible to “clutch Harry’s hand under the fur robe”.

The fifth chapter of this novella is the coldest and culminating. First, it defines the mood from the beginning: “It was a particularly cold night.” Second, in Sally Carroll’s perception, the symbol of the North is the Ice Tower, which itself is about to get lost in the confusing corridors. Third,

the protagonist will be the final point in clearing the gap with the girl’s fiancée.

We consider it necessary to refer once again to the book “Narratology”, which proposed a classification of V. Schmidt’s “plan of views”. This is a theoretical confirmation of how these views shift to the “event” side of the novel and the internal movement: 1. “The plan of space. Differences in the perception of what is happening by witnesses depend primarily on the observer’s point of view in space. It forces the observer to grasp some details of the story and ignore others” [Schmidt, 2004, 122]. As has been said many times, Sally Carroll’s perception of the North is negative on all levels. 1, p.93]

2. Ideological plan - “Witness perception (point of view) may be inconsistent, it is the result of differences in ideological point of view ... Cognition is derived from knowledge, but the view is affected by the assessment” [Schmidt, 2004, 122].

For Harry, the Ice Palace is the pinnacle of northern genius: “It is beautiful,” he cried excitedly. At first, the beauty also captivates Sally Carroll, and her mood changes, as the abstract author emphasizes:

“She took a seat on a wooden bench and the evening’s oppression lifted” [1, p.92]. But then only negative emotions appear in the story, including death motives.

3. The layer of time: “The view of time refers to the distance between the first and subsequent perception of events ... where not only the time interval between the acts of perception (acceptance) and reporting is important, but also the time interval between different time stages of perception” [Schmidt, 2004, 124]. The

novel gives clear passages of time: "The first week... And then one afternoon in every second week." had been confirmed an egg with a cracked veiny voice "[1, p.87]. the development of negative perception occurs.

4. Linguistic plan: "The witness may use in his instructions or expressions (means of expression) corresponding to his knowledge and inner state at that time, or expressions influencing the level of awareness, growing knowledge-experience and the current inner state" [Schmidt, 2004, 125]. The explanation of the nature of the human "dog-cat" also goes back to the South / North antithesis: "I never analyzed it only I just look at people and say" canine "or" feline "right off". Plus, Sally Carroll realizes that her Harry belongs to a different kind of self.

5. Perceptual plan (cognitive plan) - "The most important factor that requires the perception of events, often equated with perspective, narrative perspective or general localization - this is the prism through which events are perceived" [Schmidt, 2004, 126]. It is no coincidence that Schmidt gave his place in this classification to the "Perceptive Plan", which is "narrator - character style and price." It should be noted that the fact that the Ice Palace space is given in such an *ottenka* reflects the state of negative perception of the North by Sally Carroll. This is expressed in the negative modality of the example, in the associations and even in the theme of death: "It was an icy breath of death." [1, p.94]. The abstract author emphasizes the features of the protagonist's *tiynati* that do not allow her to sit hand in hand, while these features complete the North theme. As mentioned, the dislike of the North lasts a certain amount of time -

two weeks - and ends at the Ice Palace. In the story, the line - the two motives of the actions are clearly visible.

1. The loneliness of the protagonist in a strange space: "She was alone with this presence that came out of the North."

2. He was abandoned by his closest people on confusing roads, but Sally remembers her dear southern friends as saviors, not savages: "Clark Darrow - he would understand; or Joe Ewening; she couldn't be left here..." [1, p.95]

3. The spirit of Marjorie Lee comes as a supernatural savior and interlocutor. Naturally, this faint consciousness of the protagonist is cold, but the face is pleasant and warm: "Then some one seemed to sit down near her and take her face in warm, soft hands" [1, p.95].

Thus, at the level of the perceptual plan, her northern orientation also ends until the protagonist escapes from the ice captivity. Moreover, not only the symbol of the South is associated with the image of Marjorie Lee, but also the compositional code of the novel, i.e. the unchanging notions of the southern lady of the nineteenth century in the second and third chapters.

It is important that the abstract author emphasizes the leadership of the "south" in the rescue of Sally Carroll - "It was Dangerous Dan McGrew" and finally expresses the girl's true feelings for the South: "I'm going back home. Take me home" [1, p.96]. Again, it's clear that there's no need to cite in the text the scene where Sally and Harry open the gap, the girl's decision to go home tomorrow is enough.

The sixth chapter of *The Ice Palace* short story completely repeats the second, not

just the ending as a mirror image (color, warmth, the same characters, the same calm pace of life and the same - the same love). In this regard, we refer to W. Schmidt's study of "thematic and formal alternatives": "In a narrative substance, thematic alternatives are divided into alternatives of characters, situations and events" [Schmidt, 2004, 247]. In the first and sixth chapters, the same characters, the same situation, only in the first Sally is eating an apple, in the sixth a green peach. This situation is referred to in W. Schmidt's classification as "isopersonal alternative (belonging to the same character). W. Schmidt "Another aspect of the formal equivalence that the above changes belong to the methods that implement processes in the process of creating a narrative device: in terms of the degree of selectivity. important. In our opinion, if the pace of "lengthy" or "out-of-

event" storytelling characterizes the Southern environment, then the sequence of events, the precise timing, shows the activity and orderliness of the North.

Here are the long, lengthy sentences, the softness of the southern pronunciation that is emphasized not only in Sally, but also in Clark: "Water's warm as a kettla stream, Sally Carrol. Wanta go swimming?" [1, p.96]. The commentator gives an alternative to the "literary" pronunciation Kettla steam = kettle steam. Wanta go = Want to go (c.318)". Therefore, such an emotional completion of the novella can be a shining example of a typological structure. Topos with the strongest sign are the beginning and the end. Each event is based on the tension between situations located in its boundary areas.

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